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Correction: Intrinsic defect formation and the effect of transition metal doping on transport properties in a ductile thermoelectric material α -Ag₂S: a first-principles study

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Correction for 'Intrinsic defect formation and the effect of transition metal doping on transport properties in a ductile thermoelectric material α -Ag₂S: a first-principles study' by Ho Ngoc Nam et al., *Phys. Chem. Chem. Phys.*, 2021, DOI: 10.1039/d0cp06624a.

The published version of this manuscript included errors in eqn (8). The correct equation is shown below.

$$\mu_s \leq \mu_s^{\text{bulk}} + \Delta\mu_s$$

The Royal Society of Chemistry apologises for these errors and any consequent inconvenience to authors and readers.

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